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FER tyrosine kinase is a therapeutic target in childhood brain cancer.

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We clustered a group of childhood brain cancers together when identifying the most significant transcriptional changes in brain tumors that affect children to discover common transcriptional changes despite disparate etiologies. We identified activation of FER tyrosine kinase, a catalytically available enzyme, in childhood brain cancer. Ifebentiniib is a small molecule inhibitor of FER kinase.

1 **Results**

2 We measured total transcription in a collection of childhood brain tumors, including tumors of the ATRT,
3 pilocytic astrocytoma, glioblastoma, medulloblastoma, adamantinomatous craniopharyngioma,
4 ependymoma, ependymoma (supratentorial ZFTA-RELA fusion), ganglioma, and diffuse midline glioma.

5 GSE243682

6 *n*=5 normal brain

7 *n*=124 childhood brain tumors

8
9 We identified the tyrosine kinase FER as a common therapeutic vulnerability among childhood
10 brain tumors. FER was differentially expressed greater than 99% of the brain transcriptome.

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GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
2241	2.18e-06	0.206	-4.7360012	-0.97498961	246.018	FER	166/27159	99.4

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14 **Discussion**

15 We identified FER tyrosine kinase here as a therapeutic target in childhood brain tumors.
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Methods

We measured total transcription in childhood brain tumors using publicly available or published data and R-based computational methods.